

Study of the tribe Phaeogenini (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae, Ichneumoninae) in northern Iran, with two new genera and four new species records for the fauna of Iran

Farid Shirzadegan¹, Ali Asghar Talebi¹ &*, Matthias Riedel² & Hamidreza Hajjiganbar¹

1- Department of Entomology, Faculty of Agriculture, Tarbiat Modares University, P.O.Box: 14115-336, Tehran, Iran & 2- Zoologische Staatssammlung München, Münchenhausenstr. 21, D-81247 München, Germany.

*Corresponding author, E-mail: talebia@modares.ac.ir

Abstract

This survey was conducted as a taxonomic work on the species of the tribe Phaeogenini (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae, Ichneumoninae) in North central Iran during March to November 2010 and 2011. Nine species belonging to six genera were identified, of which two genera (i.e. *Oronotus* Wesmael, 1845 and *Stenodontus* Berthoumieu, 1897) and four species, *Dicaelotus erythrostroma* Wesmael, 1845, *Dicaelotus pudibundus* (Wesmael, 1845), *Oronotus binotatus* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Stenodontus marginellus* (Gravenhorst, 1829) are newly recorded from Iran. This work raises the number of Phaeogenini of Iran to 27 species and 13 genera. An updated list of the species in tribe Phaeogenini and detailed morphological characters of newly recorded species are also provided.

Key words: Phaeogenini, *Oronotus*, *Stenodontus*, new record, taxonomy.

مطالعه زنبورهای قبیله (Phaeogenini (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae, Ichneumoninae) در

شمال ایران همراه با گزارش دو جنس و چهار گونه جدید برای کشور

فرید شیرزادگان^۱، علی اصغر طالبی^{۱*}، ماتیاس ریدل^۲ و حمیدرضا حاجی‌قنبر^۱

۱- گروه حشره‌شناسی، دانشکده کشاورزی، دانشگاه تربیت مدرس، صندوق پستی ۳۳۶-۱۴۱۱۵، تهران، ایران و ۲- موزه جانورشناسی مونیخ، خیابان مونیخ‌هاوزن ۲۱، ۸۱۲۴۷ - d، مونیخ، آلمان.

* مسئول مکاتبات، پست الکترونیکی: talebia@modares.ac.ir

چکیده

تحقیق حاضر جهت تعیین گونه‌های قبیله (Phaeogenini (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae, Ichneumoninae) در شمال ایران طی ماه‌های اسفند تا آبان سال‌های ۱۳۸۹-۱۳۸۸ انجام گرفت. ۹ گونه متعلق به شش جنس شناسایی شدند که دو جنس (*Oronotus* Wesmael, 1845, *Stenodontus* Berthoumieu, 1897) و چهار گونه (*Dicaelotus erythrostroma* Wesmael, 1845, *Dicaelotus pudibundus* (Wesmael, 1845), *Oronotus binotatus* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Stenodontus marginellus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)) برای فون ایران جدید هستند. این تحقیق تعداد اعضای قبیله Phaeogenini ایران را به ۲۷ گونه و ۱۳ جنس افزایش داد. فهرست به روز شده قبیله Phaeogenini و صفات مرفولوژیک گونه‌های جدید ارائه گردید.

واژگان کلیدی: Phaeogenini, *Oronotus*, *Stenodontus*, گزارش جدید، رده‌بندی.

دریافت: ۹۶/۸/۲۱، پذیرش: ۹۶/۱۱/۲۱.

Introduction

The Ichneumonidae with 25292 described species is the largest family of Hymenoptera and of the class Insecta (Yu *et al.*, 2016). It almost has 9000 described species in the

Palearctic region (Riedel & Hansen, 2007). The Ichneumoninae is the second largest subfamily of Ichneumonidae, which many species are sexually different coloured and well known as endoparasitoids of Lepidoptera. The females lay their eggs into the larvae (koinobionts) or pupae (idiobionts) of hosts (Goulet & Huber, 1993). The Phaeogenini is a relatively large tribe of the subfamily Ichneumoninae including the species that are mostly small sized. They can be separated from closely related tribes of the subfamily Ichneumoninae by having circular or semicircular propodeal spiracles (a feature which is also present in some Platylabini), and also combination with morphology of head in female specimens (Tereshkin, 2009). This tribe currently includes 32 genera and about 400 species, worldwide (Yu *et al.*, 2016). Prior to this study, 13 genera and 23 species of the tribe Phaeogenini had been recorded from Iran (Diller & Schönitzer, 2003; Kolarov & Ghahari, 2005, 2008; Masnadi & Jussila, 2008b; Ghahari & Jussila, 2010b,c; Ghahari & Jussila, 2011b,c,d,e; Klopstein & Baur, 2011; Akbarzadeh, 2011; Ghahari, 2012; Ghahari *et al.*, 2012; Firuzi Jahantighi *et al.*, 2012; Barahoei *et al.*, 2013a; Kazemi *et al.*, 2014; Ghahari, 2014; Mohebban *et al.*, 2015; Diller & Riedel, 2015). In this study, we report two genera and four species of the tribe Phaeogenini for the first time from Iran. We also provide diagnostic characters, photographs and distributional data for the newly recorded species.

Materials and methods

Materials used for this work were collected by the Malaise traps installed in natural habitats in Alborz, Guilan and Tehran provinces of Iran during March to November 2010 and 2011. External morphology of the specimens were examined using an Olympus TM SZX9 stereomicroscope and diagnostic characters were illustrated on the basis of photographs taken with a Sony™ digital camera. A series of 10–15 captured images were merged into a single in-focus image using the image-stacking software Zerene Stacker version 1.04. The first, second and third authors contributed to identification of the species. The specimens are deposited in the Collection of Department of Entomology, Tarbiat Modares University (TMUC), Tehran, Iran. Morphological terminology follows Tereshkin (2009).

Results

A total of 73 specimens of the tribe Phaeogenini were collected and identified. Among them two genera (e. g. *Oronotus* Wesmael, 1845 and *Stenodontus* Berthoumieu, 1897) and four species *Dicaelotus erythrostoma* Wesmael, 1845, *Dicaelotus pudibundus* (Wesmael, 1845), *Oronotus binotatus* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Stenodontus marginellus* (Gravenhorst, 1829), are new for the Iranian fauna. The species are listed alphabetically and diagnostic characters presented for the newly recorded species.

***Centeterus confector* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Iran, Guilan province, Astaneh Ashrafiyeh, Eshamn Kamchal (37°22'06" N, 49°57'54" E, 1 m a.s.l.), 29.VIII.2010, 1 ♀, Leg.: M. Khayrandish.

General distribution: Palaearctic region (Yu *et al.*, 2016).

Distribution in Iran: Ardabil (Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008), Guilan province (current study).

***Colpognathus celerator* (Gravenhorst, 1807)**

Material examined: Iran, Guilan province, Rudsar, Ghazichak (36°45'54" N, 50°19'36" E, 1803 m a.s.l.), 28.VI.2010, 4 ♀, 5.VII.2010, 1 ♀, 23 ♀, 12.VII.2010, 3 ♀; Rudsar, Orkom (36°45'42" N, 50°18'12" E, 1235 m a.s.l.), 24.V.2010, 2 ♀, 31.V.2010, 3 ♀, leg.: M. Khayrandish.

General distribution: Palaearctic region (Yu *et al.*, 2016).

Distribution in Iran: Guilan (Kolarov & Ghahari, 2005; current study), Mazandaran (Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008); Not exactly defined (Diller & Schönitzer, 2003),

***Colpognathus grandiculus* Diller & Riedel, 2015**

Material examined: Iran, Alborz province, Karaj, Arangeh (35°55'06" N, 51°05'12" E, 1891 m a.s.l.), 24.V.2010, 1 ♀; Karaj (35°46'18" N, 50°56'42" E, 1278 m a.s.l.), 08.VI.2010, 2 ♀; Tehran province, Shahriar (35°40'06" N, 50°56'54" E, 1168 m a.s.l.), 11.V.2010, 2 ♀, 8.VI.2010, 1 ♀; Guilan province, Rudsar, Ghazichak (36°45'54" N, 50°19'36" E, 1803 m a.s.l.), 26.VII.2010, 1 ♀, 2 ♀; leg.: M. Khayrandish.

General distribution: Palaearctic region (Yu *et al.*, 2016).

Distribution in Iran: Golestan (Diller & Riedel, 2015), Alborz, Guilan and Tehran provinces (current study).

***Dicaelotus erythrostroma* Wesmael, 1845** (Fig. 1; Figs 2A–F)

Material examined: Iran, Alborz province, Karaj, Shahrestanak (35°57'36" N, 51°22'18" E, 2301 m a.s.l.), 20.VII.2010, 1 ♀; leg.: M. Khayrandish.

Diagnosis – female: Body length 5.0 mm; Head almost cubical with convex vertex (Fig. 2, A); clypeus convex, 2.33 X as wide as long, its surface with sparse punctures; face 2.6 X as wide as long, its surface densely but superficially punctured (Fig. 2, B); malar space 0.5 X as long as basal width of mandible; hypostomal and occipital carinae connected almost at mandibular base; flagellum with 27 flagellomeres and with tyloides on flagellomeres 7-14; mesonotum slightly convex, notauli absent (Fig. 2, A); scutellum slightly convex with lateral carinae (Fig. 2, E); mesopleuron densely punctured, sternaulus developed up to middle of mesopleuron (Fig. 2, D); area superomedia heart-shaped, receiving the costula behind the middle (Fig. 2, E); hind femur 3.46 X as long as its maximum width; hind tibia 1.83 X longer than hind basitarsus; postpetiole rather broad, its surface densely punctured (Fig. 2, F); length

of second metasomal tergite almost equal to its width; gastrocoeli not developed; thyridia absent; lunulae distinct (Fig. 2, F).

Coloration: body black; lateral field of face, clypeus, mandibles (excepting darkened teeth) light yellow; scape and pedicel marked with light yellow; legs red, hind femur and tibiae black apically; hind tarsi darkened; abdominal tergites narrowly reddish banded apically.

General distribution: Europe (Yu *et al.*, 2016), Western Asia – Iran (new record).

Distribution in Iran: Alborz province (current study).

Fig. 1. *Dicaelotus erythrostroma* Wesmael, 1845; male habitus, lateral view.

Fig. 2. *Dicaelotus erythrostroma* Wesmael, 1845, male; A. Head and mesonotum, dorsal view; B. Head, frontal view; C. Head, lateral view; D. Mesopleuron, lateral view; E. Scutellum and propodeum, dorsal view; F. Metasoma, dorsal view.

***Dicaelotus montanus* (de Stefani, 1885)**

Material examined: Iran, Guilan province, Astaneh Ashrafiyeh, Eshman Kamchal (37°22'06" N, 49°57'54" E, 1 m a.s.l.), 29.VIII.2010, 1 ♀; leg.: M. Khayrandish.

General distribution: Western Palaearctic region (Yu *et al.*, 2016).

Distribution in Iran: Kerman (Kazemi *et al.*, 2014), Guilan province (current study).

***Dicaelotus pudibundus* (Wesmael, 1845)** (Fig. 3; Figs 4A–G)

Material examined: Iran, Guilan province, Rudsar, Orkom (36°45'42" N, 50°18'12" E, 1235 m a.s.l.), 19.VII.2010, 1 ♀; leg.: M. Khayrandish.

Diagnosis – female: Body length 5.0 mm; Head almost cubical with convex vertex (Fig. 4, A); clypeus convex, 2.22 X as wide as long, its surface punctures; face 2.36 X as wide as long, its surface punctured and shining (Fig. 4, B); malar space about as long as basal width of mandible (Fig. 4, C); hypostomal carina connected to occipital carina at mandibular base; flagellum with 22 flagellomeres and without tyloides; mesonotum slightly convex; notauli distinct only at base of mesonotum (Fig. 4, A); scutellum slightly convex with lateral carinae; surface of mesopleuron wrinkly-punctured, shining (Fig. 4, E); area supermedia rather elongate, strongly narrowed anteriorly where it fuses into the area basalis, 1.45 X as long as wide at middle (Fig. 4, D); area dentipara of propodeum with small tooth (Fig. 4, E); hind femur 3.23 X as long as its maximum width (Fig. 4, G); hind tibia 1.76 X longer than hind basitarsus; postpetiole broad, its surface with superficial punctures; gastrocoeli and thyridia absent (Fig. 4, F).

Coloration: Head and mesosoma black; face, clypeus, antenna brown-red; pronotal ridge, pronotal base, subalarum, tegula brown-ivory; scutellum brown laterally; all legs red with the coxae and the trochanters more or less infuscate; abdominal tergites red excepting darkened petiol.

General distribution: Western Palaearctic region including Iran (new record), Lebanon and Syria (Yu *et al.*, 2016).

Distribution in Iran: Guilan province (current study).

Fig. 3. *Dicaelotus pudibundus* (Wesmael, 1845); female habitus, lateral view.

Fig. 4. *Dicaelotus pudibundus* (Wesmael, 1845), female; A. Head and mesonotum, dorsal view; B. Head, frontal view; C. Head, lateral view; D. Scutellum and propodeum, dorsal view; E. Mesopleuron, lateral view; F. Metasoma, dorsal view; G. Metasoma, lateral view.

***Heterischnus truncator* (Fabricius, 1798)**

Material examined: Iran, Tehran province, Shahriar (35°40'06" N, 50°56'54" E, 1168 m a.s.l.), 18.VIII.2010, 1, 07.IX.2010, 1, 14.IX.2010, 2, 28.IX.2010, 2, 2; Guilan province, Astaneh Ashrafiyeh, Eshman Kamchal (37°22'06" N, 49°57'54" E, 1 m a.s.l.), 13.III.2010, 1; Rudsar, Ghazichak (36°45'54" N, 50°19'36" E, 1803 m a.s.l.), 24.V.2010, 1; leg.: M. Khayrandish.

General distribution: Palearctic region (Yu *et al.*, 2016).

Distribution in Iran: Golestan, Mazandaran, Semnan (Kolarov and Ghahari, 2008), Golestan (Ghahari & Jussila, 2010b, c), Ardabil, West Azerbaijan (Ghahari & Jussila, 2011c), Tehran and Guilan provinces (current study).

Remark: This species has previously been recorded as *Rhexidermus truncator* Förster, 1889 (Ghahari & Jussila, 2010b, 2011c), which is a synonym of *Heterischnus truncator*.

***Oronotus binotatus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)** (Fig. 5, 7; Figs 6A–F, 8A–G)

Material examined: Iran, Guilan province, Astaneh Ashrafiyeh, Eshman Kamchal (37°22'06" N, 49°57'54" E, 1 m a.s.l.), 13.III.2010, 1, 2, 12.IV.2010, 2, 27.IX.2010, 2, 04.X.2010, 1, 1, 11.X.2010, 1, 1; Rudsar, Ziaz (36°52'30" N, 50°13'24" E, 490 m a.s.l.), 17.V.2010, 1, 07.VI.2010, 1; Leg.: M. Khayrandish.

Fig. 5. *Oronotus binotatus* (Gravenhorst 1829); female habitus, lateral view.

Diagnosis – female: Body length 7.0 mm; clypeus convex, 2.18 X as wide as long, its surface with sparse punctures; face 2.58 X as wide as long, its surface wrinkly-punctured (Fig. 6, B); malar space equal to width of mandible (Fig. 6, C); temple behind eyes sharply and straightly narrowed in dorsal view (Fig. 6A); flagellum with 26 flagellomeres and with white annelus on flagellomeres 8-10, first flagellomere 3 X as long as apical width in lateral view; collar of pronotum moderately long (Fig. 6, A); mesonotum slightly wider than long, notauli absent (Fig. 6, A); scutellum slightly convex, laterally carinated up to middle; surface of mesopleuron densely punctured (Fig. 6, E); area superomedia long, 2.5 X as long as its width; costulae distinct (Fig. 6, D); hind femur 4.3 X as long as its maximum width; hind tibia 2.05 X longer than hind basitarsus; postpetiole square, shining and smooth; tergite 2 strongly striated basally; gastrocoeli not developed; thyridia distinct, interspace between them longitudinally striated (Fig. 6, F).

Fig. 6. *Oronotus binotatus* (Gravenhorst 1829), female; A. Head and mesonotum, dorsal view; B. Head, frontal view; C. Head, lateral view; D. Propodeum, dorsal view; E. Mesopleuron, lateral view; F. Metasoma, dorsal view.

Fig. 7. *Oronotus binotatus* (Gravenhorst 1829); male habitus, lateral view.

Diagnosis – male: Body length 7.5-9.0 mm; similar to female but flagellum with 31 flagellomeres; metasoma with a pair of fuscous spots on tergite 2 (Fig. 8, F).

Coloration (female): Head and mesosoma black; legs red, front and middle legs basally pale, hind femur apically black, hind tibia black basally and apically, the apical tarsal segments of all legs black; tergite 1-4 red, tergite 4 sometimes black apically.

General distribution: Europe (Yu *et al.*, 2016), Western Asia – Iran (new record).

Distribution in Iran: Guilan province (current study).

Fig. 8. *Oronotus binotatus* (Gravenhorst 1829), male; A. Mesonotum and scutellum, dorsal view; B. Head, frontal view; C. Head, lateral view; D. Propodeum, dorsal view; E. Mesopleuron, lateral view; F. First and second tergites, dorsal view; G. Metasoma, lateral view.

Stenodontus marginellus (Gravenhorst, 1829) (Fig. 9; Figs 10A–E)

Material examined: Iran, Guilan province, Rudsar, Ghazichak (36°45' 54" N, 50° 19' 36" E, 1803 m a.s.l.), 24.VI.2010, 1 ♂; leg.: M. Khayrandish.

Diagnosis – male: Body length 7.0 mm; clypeus 1.77 X as wide as long; face 2.13 X as wide as long (Fig. 10, A); malar space 0.41 X as long as basal width of mandible (Fig. 10, B); temple 1.13 X as wide as transverse diameter of the eye in lateral view, roundly narrowed behind eyes in dorsal view; flagellum with 27 flagellomeres and with tyloides on

flagellomeres 3-14; mesonotum rather coarsely and sparsely punctate; scutellum slightly convex (Fig. 10, D); surface of mesopleuron punctured and shining (Fig. 10, C); area superomedia approximately with equal length and width at its middle; costulae distinct (Fig. 10, D); hind femur 3.9 X as long as its maximum width; hind tibia 1.66 X longer than hind basitarsus; postpetiole square, shining and smooth; gastrocoeli not developed; thyridia distinct (Fig. 10, E).

Fig. 9. *Stenodontus marginellus* (Gravenhorst 1829), male habitus, lateral view.

Coloration: Main color of body black; ivory or yellow: spots on middle field of face, facial orbits, frontal orbits and genal orbits, mandibles, excepting darkened teeth, hind corner of pronotum, tegula and subalarum; scutellum with lateral ivory stripes; legs reddish-brown front and middle coxae marked with ivory, hind coxa black; trochanters usually infuscate; abdominal tergites with narrow apical yellowish band.

General distribution: Palaearctic region, Iran (new record) (Yu *et al.*, 2016).

Distribution in Iran: Guilan province (current study).

Fig. 10. *Stenodontus marginellus* (Gravenhorst 1829), male; A. Head, frontal view; B. Head, lateral view; C. Mesopleuron, lateral view; D. Scutellum and propodeum, dorsal view; E. Metasoma, dorsal view.

Discussion

On the basis of this study and review of the previously published literature, 27 species belonging to 13 genera of the tribe Phaeogenini are known to occur in Iran (Table 1). The number of species recorded in Iran is still low in comparison to the known species of subfamily Ichneumoninae in the West Palaearctic region (1297 species) (Yu *et al.*, 2016). In this research, two genera (e.g. *Oronotus* Wesmael, 1845; *Stenodontus* Berthoumieu, 1897) and four species (e.g. *Dicaelotus erythrostoma* Wesmael, 1845, *Dicaelotus pudibundus* (Wesmael, 1845), *Oronotus binotatus* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Stenodontus marginellus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)) are recorded for the first time from Iran. The genus *Oronotus* Wesmael contains ten species worldwide (Yu *et al.*, 2016). Species of this genus are parasitoids of the lepidopteran families Pterophoridae, Plutellidae and Noctuidae (Yu *et al.*, 2016). The genus *Stenodontus* Berthoumieu contains 12 species in the world (Yu *et al.*, 2016). Species of this genus are parasitoids of the lepidopteran families Tortricidae, Pyralidae and Lymantriidae (Yu *et al.*, 2016). The number of species of the tribe Phaeogenini in the adjacent countries of Iran is recorded as: 440 species in former USSR (Mocsáry & Szépligeti, 1901; Roman, 1927; Uchida, 1933; Meyer, 1933; Townes, 1965; Siytan, 1977, 1979; Gokhman, 1988, 1991, 1994, 1995; Sebald *et al.*, 2000; Diller & Schönitzer, 2003; Schönitzer *et al.*, 2006), 23 species in Turkey (Diller, 1993, 1995; Kolarov, 1989, 1995b; Özdemir, 1996; Yurtcan *et al.*, 1999; Diller & Schönitzer, 2003; Gençer, 2003; Özbek, 2003; Sarıkaya & Avcı, 2005; Schönitzer *et al.*, 2006; Kolarov *et al.*, 2014b), 18 species in Azerbaijan (Aliyev, 1999), three species in Turkmenistan (Meyer, 1933; Rasnitsyn & Siytan, 1981), two species in Tajikistan (Siytan, 1977), two species in Armenia (Siytan, 1977; Diller & Schönitzer, 2003), two species in Pakistan (Diller, 1983) and one species in Afghanistan (Šedivý, 1968). Since many areas of Iran remain unexplored, we expect that the tribe Phaeogenini fauna of Iran will be substantially increased.

Table 1. Updated list of the tribe Phaeogenini (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae, Ichneumoninae) of Iran.

Phaeogenini species	Distribution in Iran (provinces)	References
<i>Aethecerus persicator</i> Aubert, 1970	Tehran	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2005; Klopffstein & Baur, 2011
<i>Centeterus confector</i> (Gravenhorst, 1829)	Ardabil; Guilan	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008; current study
<i>Centeterus major</i> Wesmael, 1845	West Azerbaijan	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008
<i>Centeterus rubiginosus</i> (Gmelin, 1790)	East Azerbaijan	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008; Ghahari & Jussila, 2011e
<i>Colpognathus celerator</i> (Gravenhorst, 1807)	Not defined; Guilan; Mazandaran	Diller & Schönitzer, 2003; Current study; Kolarov & Ghahari, 2005, Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008

<i>Colpognathus divisus</i> Thomson, 1891	Fars	Diller & Schönitzer, 2003
<i>Colpognathus grandiculus</i> Diller & Riedel, 2015	Golestan; Alborz, Guilan, Tehran	Diller & Riedel, 2015; current study
<i>Diadromus collaris</i> (Gravenhorst, 1829)	Golestan; Sistan and Baluchestan; Semnan; Kerman	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008; Ghahari & Jussila, 2011d; Firuzi Jahantighi <i>et al.</i> , 2012; Barahoei <i>et al.</i> , 2013a; Ghahari, 2012; Mohebban <i>et al.</i> , 2015
<i>Diadromus subtilicornis</i> (Gravenhorst, 1829)	Kermanshah	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008; Ghahari <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Diadromus ustalatus</i> Holmgren, 1890	East Azerbaijan	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008
<i>Diadromus varicolor</i> Wesmael, 1845	West Azerbaijan	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008; Ghahari <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Dicaelotus inflexus</i> Thomson, 1891	West Azerbaijan	Akbarzadeh, 2011
<i>Dicaelotus erythrostoma</i> Wesmael, 1845*	Alborz	current study
<i>Dicaelotus montanus</i> (de Stefani, 1885)	Kerman; Guilan	Kazemi <i>et al.</i> , 2014; current study
<i>Dicaelotus pudibundus</i> (Wesmael, 1845)*	Guilan	current study
<i>Dirophanes invisor</i> (Thunberg, 1824)	Guilan; West Azerbaijan	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008; Ghahari and Jussila, 2011e
<i>Hemichneumon subdolosus</i> Wesmael, 1857	Semnan; West Azerbaijan	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008; Ghahari & Jussila, 2011b, d
<i>Herpestomus arridens</i> (Gravenhorst, 1829)	West Azerbaijan	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008
<i>Herpestomus brunnicornis</i> (Gravenhorst, 1829)	East Azerbaijan; Tehran	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008; Ghahari <i>et al.</i> , 2012; Masnadi & Jussila, 2008b
<i>Heterischnus filiformis</i> (Gravenhorst, 1829)	Isfahan	Mohebban <i>et al.</i> , 2015
<i>Heterischnus nigricollis</i> (Wesmael, 1845)	Kermanshah; Golestan	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008; Ghahari & Jussila, 2011e
<i>Heterischnus truncator</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	Golestan, Mazandaran, Semnan; Golestan; Ardabil, West Azerbaijan; Tehran, Guilan	Kolarov and Ghahari, 2008; Ghahari & Jussila, 2010b, c; Ghahari & Jussila, 2011c; current study
<i>Oronotus binotatus</i> (Gravenhorst, 1829)*	Guilan	current study
<i>Phaeogenes heterogonus</i> Holmgren, 1860	Chaharmahal-o-Bakhtiari, Isfahan, Markazi	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008
<i>Phaeogenes melanogonos</i> (Gmelin, 1790)	Ardabil	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008
<i>Stenodontus marginellus</i> (Gravenhorst, 1829)*	Guilan	current study

<i>Tycherus ophtalmicus</i> (Wesmael, 1845)	Mazandaran; East Azerbaijan	Kolarov & Ghahari, 2008; Ghahari & Jussila, 2011d
---	--------------------------------	--

* New records for the Iranian insect fauna.

Acknowledgements

Thanks to the Department of Entomology, Tarbiat Modares University for providing financial support for this study. We are also grateful to Dr. Mohammad Khayrandish for helping us with the collecting of the specimens. We sincerely thank the editor and three anonymous reviewers for their critical review and constructive suggestions and comments.

References

- Akbarzadeh, Gh. (2011)** Identification of the pupal parasitoid wasps of grape berry moth *Lobesia botrana* (Denis and Schiffermüller) (Lep., Tortricidae) in Orumieh vineyards. *Journal of Entomological Research* 3(2), 95–102.
- Aliyev, A. A. O. (1999)** Fauna of the Subfamily Ichneumoninae (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae) of Azerbaijan with new records. *Turkish Journal of Zoology* 23, 1–12.
- Barahoei, H., Rakhshani, E., Kasparyan, D. R., Schwarz, M. & Riedel, M. (2013a)** Contribution on the knowledge of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) in the northern part of Sistan and Baluchestan province, Iran. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica*, 65(1), 131–135.
- Diller, E. & Riedel, M. (2015)** A new Phaeogenini species, *Colpognathus grandiculus*, from the Caspian region (Insecta, Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Ichneumoninae). *Mitteilungen der Münchner Entomologischen Gesellschaft* 105, 79–82.
- Diller, E. & Schönitzer, K. (2003)** Revision einiger westpalaearktischer und nearktischer Arten der Gattung *Colpognathus* Wesmael, (1845) (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Ichneumoninae, Alomyini). *Entomofauna* 24(24), 333–342.
- Diller, E. & Shaw, M. R. (2014)** Western Palaearctic Oedicephalini and Phaeogenini (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae, Ichneumoninae) in the National Museums of Scotland, with distributional data including 28 species new to Britain, rearing records, and descriptions of two new species of *Aethecerus* Wesmael and one of *Diadromus* Wesmael. *Entomologist's Gazette* 65, 109–129.
- Diller, E. (1983)** Eine neue Art der Gattung *Herpestomus* Wesmael (1845), aus Asien (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Phaeogenini). *Contributions to the American Entomological Institute* 20, 381–383.
- Diller, E. H. (1993)** Die Westpalaarktischen arten der gattung *Stenodontus* Berthoumieu 1897 (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Ichneumoninae, Phaeogenini). *Entomofauna* 14(17), 305–312.
-

- Diller, E. H. (1995)** Neues über Arten aus der Gattung *Heterischnus* Wesmael 1859, (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Ichneumoninae, Phaeogenini). *Linzer Biologische Beiträge* 27(2), 785–794.
- Firuzi Jahantighi, F., Barahoei, H., Goldasteh, Sh. & Rakhshani, E. (2012)** New records of Cryptinae Kirby 1837 and Ichneumoninae Latreille, 1802 (Insecta: Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) for Iran. *Iranian Journal of Entomological Research*, in Press.
- Gençer, L. (2003)** The parasitoids of *Yponomeuta malinellus* Zeller (Lepidoptera: Yponomeutidae) in Sivan. *Turkish Journal of Zoology* 27, 43–46.
- Ghahari, H. & Jussila, R. (2010b)** A contribution to the Ichneumon wasps (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) from Golestan National Park and vicinity, northeastern Iran. *Linzer Biologische Beiträge* 42(2), 1379–1384.
- Ghahari, H. & Jussila, R. (2010c)** Some new records of Iranian Ichneumoninae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). *Linzer Biologische Beiträge* 42(2), 1373–1377.
- Ghahari, H. & Jussila, R. (2011b)** A contribution to the knowledge of Ichneumon wasps (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonoidea: Ichneumonidae) from Azerbaijan-e-Gharbi Province, Northwestern Iran. *Linzer Biologische Beiträge* 43(2), 1277–1284.
- Ghahari, H. & Jussila, R. (2011c)** A contribution to the knowledge of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) from Arasbaran and vicinity, Iran. *Calodema* 166, 1–5.
- Ghahari, H. & Jussila, R. (2011d)** A study on the ichneumonid wasps (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) from some regions of Iran. *Linzer Biologische Beiträge* 43(1), 753–758.
- Ghahari, H. & Jussila, R. (2011e)** Five species of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) new to Iran. *Zoology in the Middle East* 52, 123–124. (Short Communication).
- Ghahari, H. (2012)** A study on the Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) from Jangal-e Abr, Semnan province, Iran. *Calodema* 201, 1–4.
- Ghahari, H. (2014)** A study on the subfamily Ichneumoninae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) from Varamin and vicinity, Iran. *Calodema* 295, 1–2.
- Ghahari, H., Fischer, M. & Jussila, R. (2012)** Braconid and ichneumonid wasps (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonoidea) as the parasitoids of *Plutella xylostella* (L.) (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae) in Iran. *Entomofauna* 33, 281–288.
- Godfray H. C. J. (1994)** Parasitoids, behavioral and evolutionary ecology. Princeton University Press, 473 pp.
- Gokhman V. E. (1991)** New species of Phaeogenini (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae) from the European part of the USSR (In Russian). *Zoologicheskii Zhurnal*. Vol. 70. No. 12. P. 73–80.
- Gokhman, V. E. (1988)** Ichneumonids of the tribe Phaeogenini (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae) of the Moscow region (In Russian). Insects of the Moscow region, problems of their registration and protection. Moscow: Nauka P. 98–127.

- Gokhman, V. E. (1994)** Parasitic wasps of the genus *Baeosemus* (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae). *Zoologicheskii Zhurnal* 73(6), 52–60.
- Gokhman, V. E. (1995)** New and little known species of ichneumon flies of the tribe Phaeoginini (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae) from the South of European Russia and adjacent territories. (In Russian with English summary). *Zoologicheskii zhurnal*. Vol. 74. No. 7. P. 51–57.
- Goulet, H. & Huber, J. (1993)** Hymenoptera of the world. An identification guid to families. Research Branch Agriculture Canada Publication 1894/E, 667 pp.
- Gupta V. K. (1987)** The Ichneumonidae of the Indo-Australian area (Hymenoptera). *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* 41, 1–1210.
- Kazemi, S., Barahoei, H. & Madjdzadeh, S. M. (2014)** First report of *Dicaelotus montanus* (di Stefani) (Ichneumonidae: Ichneumoninae) from Iran. 18th National and 6th International Congress of Biology in Iran. 26–29 August 2014, p. 45.
- Klopfstein, S. & Baur, H. (2011)** Catalogue of the type specimens of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) in the Jacques F. Aubert collection at the Musée de Zoologie, Lausanne, Switzerland. *Zootaxa* 3081, 1–90.
- Kolarov, J. & Ghahari, H. (2005)** A catalogue of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) from Iran. *Linzer biologische Beitrage* 37, 503–532.
- Kolarov, J. & Ghahari, H. (2008)** A study of the Iranian Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) III. Ichneumoninae. *Acta Entomologica Serbica* 13(1/2), 61–76.
- Kolarov, J. A. (1989)** Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) from Balkan Peninsula and Some Adjacent Regions: III. Ophioninae, Anomloninae, Metopiinae, mesochorinae, Acaenitinae, Oxytorinae, Orthopelmatinae, Collyriinae, Orthocentrinae, Diplazontinae and Ichneumoninae. *Tuerkiye Entomoloji Dergisi* 13(3), 131–140.
- Kolarov, J. A. (1995 b)** A catalogue of the Turkish Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera). *Entomofauna* 16(7), 137–188.
- Kolarov, J., Çoruh, S. & Çoruh, i. (2014b)** Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) from Anatolia. III. *Turkish Journal of Entomology* 38, 377–388.
- Masnadi, A. & Jussila, R. (2008b)** Contribution to the knowledge of ichneumonid wasps of Iran. Subfamilies Ichneumoninae, Pimplinae and Diplazontinae (Hyemnoptera, Ichneumonidae). *Entomofauna* 29(22), 293–320.
- Meyer, N. F. (1933)** Keys to parasitic Hymenoptera (family Ichneumonidae) of the USSR and adjacent countries. Vol. 1. Introduction and Ichneumoninae. *Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR* 9(1), 1–458.
- Mocsáry, A. & Szépligeti, G. (1901)** Hymenopteren. Pp 121–169 in: HORVATH, G. (ed.) Dritte Asiatische Forschungsreise des Grafen Eugen Zichy. Karl W. Hiersemann, Leipzig. 472 pp.

- Mohebban, S., Takalloozadeh, H., Barahoei, H. & Madjdzadeh, M. (2015)** New records of Cryptinae and Ichneumoninae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) species from Kerman province, Southeast Iran. *Journal of Crop Protection* 4(3), 337–349.
- Özbek, H., Çoruh, S. & Kolarov, J. (2003)** A contribution to the Ichneumonidae fauna of Turkey. Subfamily Ichneumoninae (Hymenoptera). *Entomofauna* 24(10), 157–163.
- Özdemir, Y. (1996)** Species of ichneumonid wasps of the subfamilies Banchinae and Ichneumoninae (Hym.: Ichneumonidae) from Central Anatolia. *Bulletin of Plant Protection* 36(3–4), 91–103.
- Perkins, J. F. (1959)** Hymenoptera. Ichneumonoidea. Ichneumonidae, key to subfamilies and Ichneumoninae-1. Handbooks for the Identification of British Insects 7(2ai), 1–116.
- Rasnitsyn, A. P. & Siytan, U. V. (1981)** A guide to the insects of the European part of the USSR. Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae. Subfamily Ichneumoninae. (in Russian), *Opredeliteli Faune SSSR* 3(3), 505–636.
- Riedel, M. & Hansen, L. O. (2007)** Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) new for the fauna of Norway, Part 3. *Norwegian Journal of Entomology* 54, 59–64.
- Roman, A. (1927)** Entomologische Ergebnisse der schwedischen Kamtschatka-Expedition 1920-1922. 10. Ichneumonidae, Subfam. Ichneumoninae. *Arkiv for Zoologi* 19 (7), 1–19.
- Sarıkaya, O. & Avcı, M. (2005)** Studies on the parasitoid complex of *Choristoneura murinana* (Hbn.) (Lep.: Tortricidae) in Turkey. *Journal of Pest Science* 78(2), 63–66.
- Schönitzer, K., Hower, E., Melzer, R. R. & Diller, E. (2006)** Taxonomie und vergleichende Morphologie der Gattung *Dirophanes* Foerster, 1869 (Ichneumonidae, Ichneumoninae, Phaeogenini). *Mitteilungen der Münchner Entomologischen Gesellschaft* 95, 87–142.
- Sebald, H., Schönitzer, K. & Diller, E. (2000)** Eine neue Art der Gattung *Aethecerus* Wesmael, [1845] aus der Ostpaläarkt (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Alomyini). *Entomofauna* 21 (28), 313–319.
- Šedivý, J. (1968)** Beiträge zur Kenntnis der Fauna Afghanistans. Ichneumonidae, Hym. *Casopis Moravského Musea. Supplement* 53, 249–272.
- Siytan, U. V. (1977)** A review of the tribe Phaeogenini (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae) in the European regions of the USSR. *Entomologicheskoye Obozreniye* 56(4), 843–854.
- Siytan, U. V. (1979)** A new Ichneumonidae of the tribe Phaeogenini (Hymenoptera) (in Russian). *Trudy Vsesoyuznogo Entomologicheskogo Obshchestva* 61, 135–136.
- Tereshkin, A. (2009)** Illustrated key to the Ichneumoninae tribes and Platylabini genera of world fauna (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Ichneumoninae). *Linzer Biologische Beiträge* 41(2), 1317–1608.
- Townes, H. K., Momoi, S. & Townes, M. (1965)** A catalogue and reclassification of the eastern Palearctic Ichneumonidae. *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute*. No.5. 661pp.

- Uchida, T. (1933)** Über die Schmarotzerhymenopteren von *Grapholitha molesta* Busck. in Japan. *Insecta Matsumurana* 7,153–164.
- Yu, D. S., Van Achterberg, K. & Horstmann, K. (2016)** World Ichneumonoidea, 2015. Taxonomy, Biology, Morphology and Distribution. On USB Flash drive. www.taxapad.com, Nepean, Ontario Canada.
- Yurtcan, M., Beyarslan, A. & Kolarov, J. (1999)** Investigations on the Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) fauna of Turkey. V. Diplazontinae and Ichneumoninae. *Acta Entomologica Bulgarica* 5(1), 34–36.
-